

Study of base line environmental data of multimetal mining with special reference to Ambaji Mine

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Abstract : Any mining activity is likely to affect the quality of surrounding environment during its operation. The nature and magnitude of impacts on different components of the environment, viz. air, noise, water, land, biological and socio-economic vary depending on the nature and size of the mining project and therefore it is essential to find out the base line environmental data before preparing the environmental management plan. Environment management plan gives the account of measures necessary to prevent the impacts on the baseline environmental situations. Once the base line status of environmental parameters is known the decision regarding corrective and preventive measures becomes more scientific and technologically and financially viable. In present study efforts are made to establish the base line air and water quality of Ambaji Multi Metal Mine at Distt. Banaskantha, Gujarat. Therefore this study will be useful for making the decisions regarding the environmental measures required by the mining activity.

Keywords : Ground water, surface water, soil, air impacts, ambient air quality, environmental management plan.

Introduction

The study was carried out near the multimetal mine at Ambaji, Distt. Banaskantha, Gujarat. A 10 km radius area, which comprises villages' i.e. residential area, forest and industrial areas, from the core mining site was first selected and than air quality was monitored using the high volume sampler. The sampling network was designed keeping in view the prevailing wind directions¹ and potential impact zones around the proposed project site. Based on this, eight ambient air quality-monitoring stations³ were selected and monitoring was carried out twice in a week at each sampling station for three months during the summer season year 2010 as summer is a critical season from environmental pollution dispersion point of view. At all these stations, suspended particulate matter (SPM) was monitored on 24 hourly basis.

Similarly the underground and surface water samples were analysed for knowing the physico-chemical parameters viz. physical, inorganic, organic and nutrients and heavy metals in laboratory. The study area map is shown in Fig. 1.

Experimental

Air environment :

The SPM¹ was monitored by gravimetric method using high volume sampler. The Whatman glass fiber filter paper ¹GS/A was first maintained at 20 °C for 24 h and then weighed². The filter paper was then fitted to the High Volume Sampler and samples were collected at 1200 L/m in for 24 h. Filter paper was again weighed and amount of particulate matter per unit volume are calculated.

SO₂ and NO_x was found out using pulse fluorescent instrument and chemiluminescence instrument respectively.

Water environment :

Physico-chemical analysis of water⁴ :

Turbidity was measured using Hach model 2100 P Turbidimeter², pH and electrical conductivity (EC) were determined using Hach model pH meter and SENSION conductivity meter respectively, total solids, suspended solids (TS), dissolved solids (TDS) were determined by standard gravimetric analysis.

Organic and nutrient parameter :

Dissolved oxygen (DO) was calculated by standard

Fig. 1. Study area map with monitoring locations.

Winkler method, phosphate was determined by Hach model 2010 spectrophotometer using Phosver 3 ascorbic acid method (range 0.00 to 2.50 mg/L), chemical oxygen demand (COD) was determined by standard reflux method.

Chemical analysis⁴ :

Alkalinity (HCO_3^-) was estimated by titrating with standard sulfuric acid, chlorides (Cl^-) was determined by titration with standard silver nitrate, using potassium chromate as an indicator, sulphate (SO_4^{2-}) were precipitated as BaSO_4 in acidic media (HCl) with barium chloride. The absorption of light by this precipitated suspension was measured by spectrophotometer at 450 nm, calcium

and magnesium hardness was determined by standard complexometric titration (EDTA titration method), fluorides (F^-) were estimated by spectrophotometric method using Hach model 2010 (Standard SPADNS method), nitrogen (ammonia) was determined by spectrophotometer (Hach model 2010) by Standard Nessler method.

Heavy metal analysis⁴ :

The following metals were analysed using Atomic Absorption Spectrophotometer double beam Perkin-Elmer USA make model 372. The absorbance for cadmium, chromium, copper, manganese, iron, lead, zinc was measured at standard wavelength.

Results and discussion

Air environment :

The criteria taken into account in the design of ambient air quality monitoring network were the priority area for air monitoring were identified by running the screening air quality models like PTMAX (Point Maximum), PTPLU (Point Plume) and PTDIS (Point Distance), PAL (Point Area and Line)³ and using available meteorological data, topography/terrain of the study area, density of population within the region, residential and sensitive areas, magnitude of surrounding activities, wind direction and wind speed.

To establish the existing baseline air quality status of the air basin, around Ambaji region, various Ambient Air Quality Monitoring (AAQM) stations were selected in different directions of proposed project site as per guidelines of network sitting criteria. Based on the nature of mining activities and various other activities within the study area, the conventional air pollutant suspended particulate matter was identified as significant pollutants for ambient air quality monitoring.

During the summer season, the 95th percentile value of 24 hourly concentration of SPM was found to be in the range of 166.6 to 180 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$. The maximum observed SPM concentration of 180.0 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ was found at Godatakni. It is attributed to the near by Marble mining activities and Marble mining. The minimum observed SPM of 116.6 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ was found at village Chapri. The SPM concentration observed Ambaji mine site was in the range of 102.4 to 177 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ which is well within the stipulated regulatory limits. The different percentiles along with minimum and maximum SPM concentrations observed in the study area are given in Table 1.

Water environment :

Ground water quality :

Fourteen ground water samples were collected from different villages surrounding the project site and analysis was carried out (Tables 2.1 and 2.2).

Analytical results indicate variation² of pH in the range of 6.7 to 8.4. The conductivity values were in the range of 0.45 to 2.28 mS/cm. The turbidity values were found in the range of 0.53 to 7.81 NTU. Total dissolved solids observed were in the range of 291 to 1149 mg/L and suspended solids varied from 12 to 48 mg/L.

The sulphate and chloride values³ were found to be between 12 to 1000 mg/L and 37 to 424 mg/L respectively. The concentration of nitrate and fluoride shows variation in the range of 1.7 to 9.8 mg/L and 0.5 to 2.1 mg/L respectively. Total hardness has been found in the range of 223 to 893 mg/L.

The heavy metals are found in considerably low concentrations. The concentration of iron at Koteswar is found to be 0.92 mg/L this may be due to geological formation of the area. Chromium and cadmium were present in non-detectable range in all the ground water samples. Results of heavy metal analysis are given in Table 2.2.

Surface water quality :

Five surface water samples were collected and analysed (Tables 2.3 and 2.4). The pH of the water has been found to be in the range of 5.2 to 8.2. Turbidity has been found in the range of 0.51 to 3.21 NTU. Conductivity was observed in the range of 0.43 to 3.87 mS/cm, total dis-

Table 1. Observed values of ambient SPM concentration (Summer season)

Sl. no.	24 hourly average Sampling stations	Distance from core zone in km	Min. obs.	Unit : $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$			Max. obs.
				Percentile			
				25	50	95	
1.	Ambaji mine site (core zone)	Reference point	102.4	131.6	148.5	174.7	177.0
2.	Godatakni	1.7	105.3	130.0	142.5	180.0	182.5
3.	Koteswar	4.0	93.2	103.9	119.1	134.5	135.0
4.	Khumbhariya	3.5	114.0	123.8	139.5	162.9	164.3
5.	Chapri	4.5	108.0	109.2	112.7	116.6	117.0
6.	Jambudi	8.5	95.0	99.6	106.3	124.7	126.1
7.	Ranpur	8.0	102.0	105.5	115.0	125.8	126.0
8.	Sebalpani	5.5	120.1	123.7	130.7	142.16	144.2
9.	Uplibor	8.0	98.0	105.6	111.3	124.2	126.8

Table 2.1. Ground water – physical and inorganic parameters (Summer season)

Location	pH	Turbidity (NTU)	Conductivity (mS/cm)	TDS (mg/L)	SS (mg/L)	TS (mg/L)	Alkalinity as CaCO ₃	Hardness as CaCO ₃			SO ₄ ²⁻	Cl ⁻	Na ⁺	F ⁻	K ⁺
								T	Ca	Mg					
Min	8.3	2.11	0.59	291	12	303	218	242	130	112	18	37	45	2.4	1.2
Jambudi	7.7	2.64	0.63	310	20	330	190	251	130	121	19	37	41	3.4	1.7
Koteshwar	7.9	1.40	1.01	495	28	523	133	344	186	158	58	138	79	4.4	0.6
Kumbhariya	8.3	0.54	0.76	373	44	417	123	558	186	372	74	230	76	4.5	0.8
Chhapri	8.4	0.78	0.45	217	16	233	171	167	84	83	12	46	47	2.5	1.8
Taleti	8.2	1.69	1.39	692	32	724	275	423	139	284	75	207	133	2.6	1.1
Ranpur	7.7	7.81	1.64	817	20	837	209	363	167	196	65	313	279	1.7	1.5
Chikla	8.1	2.11	1.05	518	24	542	161	418	204	214	160	97	60	6.0	1.4
Baldihar	7.6	0.90	0.95	464	48	512	256	325	121	204	28	78	81	1.5	0.50
Bedopani	8.2	0.53	0.92	451	40	491	161	325	158	167	43	87	69	4.4	2.1
Surpagla	7.6	1.37	2.28	1149	12	1161	133	660	372	288	110	424	153	9.8	0.6
Padlia	6.5	1.23	1.46	723	12	735	161	558	363	195	75	198	51	7.9	1.5
Panchha	6.7	1.10	0.60	291	36	327	209	223	158	65	26	64	60	2.5	1.4
GMDC Nursery	6.7	0.85	1.21	597	32	629	171	893	577	316					

Note : All values are expressed in mg/L.

Table 2.2. Ground water – heavy metals (Summer season)

Sl. no.	Location	Fe	Ni	Zn	Cu	Co	Pb	Mn
1.	Min	0.18	0.01	0.12	0.22	0.02	ND	0.20
2.	Jambudi	0.17	0.01	0.10	0.20	ND	0.01	0.17
3.	Koteshwar	0.92	0.11	0.01	0.27	ND	0.01	0.10
4.	Kumbhariya	0.19	0.03	0.06	0.19	0.02	0.01	ND
5.	Gujarat chhapri	0.11	ND	0.02	0.15	0.02	ND	0.20
6.	Taleti	0.16	0.02	0.09	0.19	0.01	0.02	0.10
7.	Ranpur	0.15	ND	0.11	0.21	0.02	ND	0.11
8.	Chikla	0.18	ND	0.06	0.20	ND	ND	0.15
9.	Baldihar	0.17	0.03	0.08	ND	0.01	ND	ND
10.	Bedopani	0.88	ND	0.01	0.19	0.01	0.02	0.10
11.	Surpagla	0.10	0.04	0.07	0.23	ND	ND	0.14
12.	Padlia	0.19	0.01	0.08	ND	ND	ND	0.09
13.	Panchha	0.18	ND	0.09	0.18	ND	0.01	0.08
14.	GMDC Nursery	0.08	ND	0.75	3.82	ND	0.01	0.10

All values are expressed in mg/L.

The concentration of Cr and Cd is found below detectable limit.

Table 2.3. Surface water – physical and inorganic parameters (Summer season)

Location	pH	Turbidity (NTU)	Conductivity (mS/cm)	TDS (mg/L)	SS (mg/L)	TS (mg/L)	Alkalinity as CaCO ₃	Hardness as CaCO ₃			SO ₄ ²⁻	Cl ⁻	Na ⁺	F ⁻	K ⁺
								T	Ca	Mg					
Saraswati river	7.8	1.06	0.52	250	52	302	152	130	74	56	13	64	68	0.5	1.0
Teliya river (on way to Sabalpani and Balaram)	8.2	1.11	0.43	206	132	338	171	158	65	93	13	41	62	2.1	1.9
Teliya River (on way to Abu Road)	8.5	0.75	0.45	218	16	234	161	177	84	93	9	46	76	1.9	3.3

Table-2.3 (contd.)

Acid Mine water	5.2	3.21	3.87	2000	68	2068	66	2604	930	1674	4300	55	56	Nil	32
Dam Water, GMDC	7.6	0.51	1.22	601	64	665	351	446	279	167	145	106	106	0.8	2.4

Note : All values are expressed in mg/L.

Table 2.4. Surface water – organic and nutrient parameter and heavy metals (Summer season)

Location	COD	PO ₄ ³⁻	NH ₃ -N	BOD	Fe	Ni	Zn	Cu	Co	Pb	Mn
Saraswati river	9	0.43	ND	<5	0.15	ND	0.06	0.21	0.04	0.01	0.20
Teliya river (on way to Sabalpani and Balaram)	19	0.38	ND	<5	0.21	0.01	0.14	ND	0.02	ND	0.20
Teliya river (on way to Abu Road)	16	0.37	ND	<5	0.10	ND	0.05	0.17	ND	0.02	0.10
Acid Mine water	215	0.78	ND	20	0.17	0.55	15.0	14.3	1.00	0.02	20.1
Dam Water, GMDC	10	0.75	ND	<5	0.19	ND	0.11	0.17	0.03	ND	0.19

Note : All values are expressed in mg/L.

The concentration of Cr and Cd is found below detectable limit.

solved solids have been found in the range of 206 to 2000 mg/L and suspended solids have been found in the range of 16 to 132 mg/L in the samples.

The alkalinity⁵ has been found to be in the range of 66 to 351 mg/L in sample of surface water collected from Acid Mine Water and Dam Water. Total hardness, sulphate and chloride were found to be in the range of 130 and 2604, 9 and 4300 and 41 and 106 mg/L respectively. The concentration of fluoride is in the range of 0 to 2.1 mg/L.

From these results it may be concluded that the quality of air and water samples is well within limits prescribed by the statutory authorities.

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